

Deep Learning

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Abstract

Since a few years, we hear about Artificial Intelligence, Big data, Machine learning etc... Many concepts made possible by the increase in the number of data, the computing power and more recently by the use of new algorithmic techniques: Deep learning... but what is Deep Learning? Deep learning is an emerging area of machine learning (ML) research. It comprises multiple hidden layers of artificial neural networks. Deep learning models are vaguely inspired by information processing and communication patterns in biological nervous systems yet have various differences from the structural and functional properties of biological brains. Neural networks and deep learning currently provide the best solutions to many problems in image recognition, speech recognition, natural language processing and many other fields... What are the limits of this technology? How far can humanity benefit? Questions that still remain unanswered ...

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